

MODELLING AND ANALYSIS OF THE TI/AL SOLID PHASE REACTIVE DIFFUSION BONDING

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ABSTRACT

A theoretical model is developed based on the solid phase diffusion bonding mechanism for isothermal reactive diffusion between Ti and Al, and solved in the temperature range of 793K-848K. The analytical results show that the Ti atoms and Al atoms are mainly used to synthesize TiAl₃(β) phase due to the facts that both the inter-diffusion coefficients of Al in Ti solid solution phase (α) and Ti in Al solid solution phase (γ) are very small and the solubility of Ti in γ phase is very low. β phase grows mainly towards Al side and its growth kinetics is controlled by the inter-diffusion coefficient of β phase which is determined mainly by the grain boundary diffusion.

1 INTRODUCTION

Some materials prepared through Ti/Al solid phase reactive diffusion bonding, such as Ti/Al composites, Ti/TiAl₃ composites and γ -TiAl intermetallic compound, are commonly used in aerospace, automobile and chemical engineering because of their superior properties [1-3]. It is therefore important to investigate the solid reactive diffusion mechanism and the reactive kinetics between Ti and Al. The topic has attracted many researchers and a common observation is that there is only one intermetallic compound TiAl₃ formed in the diffusion zone. Several studies systemically investigated the mechanism and kinetics of the intermetallic layer growth during solid-state reaction. However the reported data such as kinetics exponent, growth rate and activation energy vary widely among different studies [4-11].

In the present work, a theoretical model is developed based on the solid phase diffusion bonding mechanism. The concentration profiles of Al in all phases are demonstrated and the parabolic coefficient of TiAl₃ are calculated. Based on these analytical results, the growth kinetics of TiAl₃ phase and the reaction mechanism are discussed.

2 THE TI/AL DIFFUSION BONDING MECHANISM

According to the experimental results in the studies [4-11], the Ti/Al solid phase reactive diffusion mechanism is summarized and shown in Figure 1. In the first stage, the real contact area of Ti/Al diffusion couple is augmented under integrated influence of temperature and pressure. At the same time, the surface oxide films are cracked and the generated fresh surface is bonded (Fig. 1a). In the second stage, inter-diffusion of Ti and Al occurs, and γ and α solid solution phase are generated (Fig. 1b). In the third stage, the Ti/Al diffusion reaction begins and the TiAl₃ nucleates when the concentration ratio reaches that of TiAl₃. Firstly, TiAl₃ phase exists in the form of particles, and then is formed in the form of sheets owing to transverse diffusion (Fig. 1c). In the last stage, TiAl₃ begins to grow towards the regions of both Ti and Al, and is the only phase in the case of sufficient supply and diffusion of element Al. In the most cases, the relationship between the thickness of TiAl₃ layer and annealing time is compatible with parabolic law (Fig. 1d).

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of the Ti/Al solid phase diffusion bonding.

3 THEORETICAL MODEL AND PARAMETER SETTING

3.1 Theoretical model

In order to establish a theoretical model for the Ti/Al reactive diffusion bonding, the following assumptions are made: the thickness is semi-infinite for α and γ phases; the inter-diffusion coefficients of α , β and γ phases are independent of composition and just a function of temperature; the nucleation stage of β phase is ignored since it usually occurs at a very short period of time with respect to the total annealing time[2]; the interface of each phase is flat, and the inter-diffusion of elements Ti and Al occurs along the direction perpendicular to the flat interface; the concentration of the interface is at local equilibrium, and the equilibrium concentration may be obtained by the Ti-Al binary alloy phase diagram. When the Ti/Al diffusion couples are annealed at temperature T for an appropriate period of time t with T is high enough for the reaction diffusion to take place sufficiently fast but lower than the temperature at which the liquid phase becomes stable, the concentration profiles of Al element across all of phases along the diffusion direction is shown in Figure 2. In this figure, α , γ represent the primary solid solution phase of Ti and Al, respectively, β is the intermetallic compound TiAl_3 ; the coordinate indicates the composition c of element Al, the abscissa shows the distance x ; the dashed lines and solid lines show the concentration profiles before and after annealing, respectively; $z^{\beta\gamma}$ and $z^{\alpha\beta}$ indicate the migration distance of γ/β and β/α interface from the initial interface position after annealing; $c^{\gamma 0}$ and $c^{\alpha 0}$ are the initial concentration of γ and α phase, and $c^{\beta\gamma}$ and $c^{\gamma\beta}$ are the concentrations of β and γ phases, respectively, at the γ/β interface, and $c^{\alpha\beta}$ and $c^{\beta\alpha}$ are the concentrations of α and β phases, respectively, at the α/β interface. The $c^{\gamma 0}$ and $c^{\alpha 0}$ provide the initial conditions, and those $c^{\beta\gamma}$, $c^{\gamma\beta}$, $c^{\alpha\beta}$ and $c^{\beta\alpha}$ give the boundary conditions.

Figure 2: Schematic diagram of concentration profiles of element Al in α , β and γ phases.

For the reactive diffusion governed by the volume diffusion or the volume and grain boundary mixed diffusion without grain growth, the positions $z^{\alpha\beta}$ and $z^{\beta\gamma}$ of the α/β and γ/β interface are described as functions of the annealing time t by the following equations [12-13].

$$z^{\alpha\beta} = K^{\beta\alpha} \sqrt{4D^\beta t} = K^{\alpha\beta} \sqrt{4D^\alpha t} \quad (1)$$

$$z^{\beta\gamma} = K^{\beta\gamma} \sqrt{4D^\beta t} = K^{\gamma\beta} \sqrt{4D^\gamma t} \quad (2)$$

Here, D^α , D^β and D^γ are the inter-diffusion coefficients in α , β and γ phases, respectively, and $K^{\beta\alpha}$, $K^{\alpha\beta}$, $K^{\beta\gamma}$ and $K^{\gamma\beta}$ are the dimensionless proportionality coefficients. The composition c for α , β and γ phases is expressed as a function of the distance and the annealing time by the following equations [14].

$$C^\alpha = C^{\alpha 0} + \frac{C^{\alpha\beta} - C^{\alpha 0}}{1 - \operatorname{erf}(K^{\beta\alpha} \sqrt{D^\beta / D^\alpha})} \times \{1 - \operatorname{erf}(\frac{x}{\sqrt{4D^\alpha t}})\}, x > z^{\alpha\beta}, \quad (3)$$

$$C^\beta = \frac{C^{\beta\gamma} \operatorname{erf}(K^{\beta\alpha}) - C^{\beta\alpha} \operatorname{erf}(K^{\beta\gamma})}{\operatorname{erf}(K^{\beta\alpha}) - \operatorname{erf}(K^{\beta\gamma})} + \frac{C^{\beta\alpha} - C^{\beta\gamma}}{\operatorname{erf}(K^{\beta\alpha}) - \operatorname{erf}(K^{\beta\gamma})} \operatorname{erf}(\frac{x}{\sqrt{4D^\beta t}}), z^{\beta\gamma} < x < z^{\alpha\beta}, \quad (4)$$

and

$$C^\gamma = C^0 + \frac{C^{\gamma\beta} - C^{\gamma 0}}{1 + \operatorname{erf}(K^{\beta\gamma} \sqrt{D^\beta / D^\gamma})} \times \{1 + \operatorname{erf}(\frac{x}{\sqrt{4D^\gamma t}})\}, x < z^{\beta\gamma}. \quad (5)$$

Here, $K^{\beta\alpha}$, $K^{\beta\gamma}$ can be solved by the transcendental equation as follows.

$$C^{\beta\alpha} - C^{\alpha\beta} = \frac{C^{\alpha 0} - C^{\alpha\beta}}{K^{\beta\alpha} \sqrt{D^\beta / D^\alpha} \sqrt{\pi} \{1 - \operatorname{erf}(K^{\beta\alpha} \sqrt{D^\beta / D^\alpha})\}} \times \exp\{-(K^{\beta\alpha})^2 D^\beta / D^\alpha\} + \frac{C^{\beta\gamma} - C^{\beta\alpha}}{K^{\beta\alpha} \sqrt{\pi} \{\operatorname{erf}(K^{\beta\alpha}) - \operatorname{erf}(K^{\beta\gamma})\}} \exp\{-(K^{\beta\alpha})^2\}, \quad (6)$$

and

$$C^{\gamma\beta} - C^{\beta\gamma} = \frac{C^{\beta\alpha} - C^{\beta\gamma}}{K^{\beta\gamma} \sqrt{\pi} \{\operatorname{erf}(K^{\beta\alpha}) - \operatorname{erf}(K^{\beta\gamma})\}} \exp\{-(K^{\beta\gamma})^2\} + \frac{C^{\gamma 0} - C^{\gamma\beta}}{K^{\beta\gamma} \sqrt{D^\beta / D^\gamma} \sqrt{\pi} \{1 + \operatorname{erf}(K^{\beta\gamma} \sqrt{D^\beta / D^\gamma})\}} \exp\{-(K^{\beta\gamma})^2 D^\beta / D^\gamma\}. \quad (7)$$

As seen from Fig. 2, the thickness l of the β phase is the difference between $z^{\alpha\beta}$ and $z^{\beta\gamma}$, which is described as a function of t by the equation.

$$l^2 = (z^{\alpha\beta} - z^{\beta\gamma})^2 = 4D^\beta (K^{\beta\alpha} - K^{\beta\gamma})^2 t = Kt \quad (8)$$

Here, K is the parabolic coefficient of β phase with a dimension of m^2/s . From the above equation, K is a function of D^β , $K^{\beta\alpha}$ and $K^{\beta\gamma}$. Furthermore, $K^{\beta\alpha}$ and $K^{\beta\gamma}$ are functions of $C^{\alpha 0}$, $C^{\alpha\beta}$, $C^{\beta\alpha}$, $C^{\beta\gamma}$, $C^{\gamma\beta}$, $C^{\gamma 0}$, D^α , D^β and D^γ . The effects of these parameters on the growth rate were quantitatively evaluated in the present analysis.

3.2 Parameter setting

In the above theoretical model, the concentration c of Al is described in the mol per unit volume. On the other hand, the mol fraction y of element Al is in practically used to express the composition of each phase in the Ti-Al binary alloy phase diagram. The mol fraction y is readily converted into the concentration c by the equation $c=y/V_m$, where, V_m is the molar volume of the relevant phase. The molar volumes of Ti, Al and TiAl_3 are 10.6, 10.0 and $9.6\text{cm}^3/\text{mol}$, respectively [15]. Since the differences between molar volumes are usually negligible compared with those between the inter-

diffusion coefficients, $c^{\alpha 0}$, $c^{\alpha\beta}$, $c^{\beta\alpha}$, $c^{\beta\gamma}$, $c^{\gamma\beta}$ and $c^{\gamma 0}$ can be replaced with $y^{\alpha 0}$, $y^{\alpha\beta}$, $y^{\beta\alpha}$, $y^{\beta\gamma}$, $y^{\gamma\beta}$ and $y^{\gamma 0}$, respectively[12]. For polycrystalline diffusion, the grain boundary diffusion cannot be ignored when the grain size is small. Both the volume and grain boundary diffusions can be expressed using the classic Arrhenius relationship below [16].

$$D_v = D_{0v} \exp\left(\frac{-Q_v}{RT}\right) \quad (9)$$

$$D_{gb} = D_{0gb} \exp\left(\frac{-Q_{gb}}{RT}\right) \quad (10)$$

Here, D_v is the volume diffusion coefficient, D_{gb} is the grain boundary diffusion coefficient, and D_{0v} and D_{0gb} are pre-exponent factors of volume diffusion and grain boundary diffusion, respectively. Usually D_{0v} is equal to D_{0gb} . Q_v and Q_{gb} are activation energy of volume diffusion and grain boundary diffusion, respectively. Usually Q_{gb} is equal to 0.4-0.6 Q_v [17]. The overall effective diffusion coefficient D can be calculated as weighted average of grain boundary diffusion and volume diffusion contributions by the following equation.

$$D = fD_{gb} + (1-f)D_v \quad (11)$$

Here, f is the volume fraction of grain boundary in the polycrystalline and can be expressed as $f=q\delta/d$, q is a numerical factor depending on the grain shape with $q=3$ for equiaxed grain and $q=1$ for columnar grain, δ is the width of grain boundary, which is approximately equal to 0.5nm, d is the grain size [17].

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Below the melting point of Al, especially in the temperature range of 793-848K, the thickness of TiAl₃ follows parabolic law with annealing time[6, 7, 11] as the growth rate of the grains is slow. Therefore, the growth kinetics of TiAl₃ intermetallic compound in the temperature range of 793-848K can be analytically calculated by using the above theoretical model. According to the Ti-Al binary alloy phase diagram [18], the interface concentrations $y^{\beta\beta}$, $y^{\beta\gamma}$, $y^{\beta\alpha}$, $y^{\alpha\beta}$ are 0.9963, 0.7490, 0.7450, 0.1110 at 793K, 0.9957, 0.7490, 0.7450, 0.1170 at 823K, 0.9952, 0.7490, 0.7450, 0.1210 at 848K, respectively, assuming that diffusion couple is pure Ti and pure Al, the initial concentration $y^{\gamma 0}$ and $y^{\alpha 0}$ is 1 and 0, respectively. Moreover, as the solubility of Ti in γ phase is very low, the grain size of γ phase is usually large, and then the grain boundary diffusion in γ phase is not considered in the temperature range of 793-848K. The volume fraction of grain boundary is taken to be $f=0$; the pre-exponent factor of γ phase is taken to be $D_{\gamma 0v}=1.12\times 10^{-1}$ m²/s; the activation energy of volume diffusion of γ phase is taken to be $Q_{\gamma v}=260.0$ kJ/mol [19]. However, the grain boundary diffusion in β and α need to be considered as the size of grains of β and α phase is little during the annealing. Since the shape and size of the grains of β and α phase are different and change slowly during the annealing, to simplify the discussion, it is assumed that the shape of the grain is columnar crystal with $q=1$, and the grain size is constant which is the average size of the grains in the bonding process. To calculate the effective diffusion coefficient of α phase, the pre-exponent factor $D_{\alpha 0v}=1.4\times 10^{-2}$ m²/s, the activation energy of volume diffusion $Q_{\alpha v}=326.0$ kJ/mol [20] and the activation energy of grain boundary diffusion $Q_{\alpha gb}=0.62 Q_{\alpha v}$ [21] are available. To calculate the effective diffusion coefficient of the β phase, the pre-exponent factor $D_{\beta 0v}=6\times 10^{-6}$ m²/s, the activation energy of volume diffusion $Q_{\beta v}=165.88$ kJ/mol [22] are available. However, the activation energy of grain boundary diffusion of β phase $Q_{\beta gb}$ has not been reported in the literature, and in this paper, three values of $Q_{\beta gb}$ are used, i.e. $0.4 Q_{\beta v}$, $0.5 Q_{\beta v}$, and $0.6 Q_{\beta v}$.

The calculated values of D^α , D^β , D^γ , $K^{\beta\gamma}$, $K^{\beta\alpha}$, K and other parameters under the conditions of different temperatures, grain sizes and activation energies of grain boundary diffusion are shown in Table 1. According to Eq.9, the values of the volume inter-diffusion coefficient of β phase are 7.20×10^{-17} , 1.80×10^{-16} , 3.67×10^{-16} m²/s at 793, 823, 848K, respectively, which are much lower than the effective inter-diffusion coefficient D^β from Eq.11 under the conditions of different grain size and

activation energy at the same temperature (Table 1), and the values of the volume inter-diffusion coefficient of α phase are 4.70×10^{-24} , 2.85×10^{-23} , $1.16 \times 10^{-22} \text{m}^2/\text{s}$ at 793, 823, 848K, respectively, which are also much lower than the effective inter-diffusion coefficient D^α from Eq.11 under the conditions of different grain size and activation energy at the same temperature (Table 1). This implies that grain boundary diffusion is predominant in β and α phase in the temperature range of 793-848K. In the case of rate-controlling by grain boundary diffusion without grain growth, the thickness of interface layer also follows parabolic law with annealing time [12]. It is seen from Table 1 that the signs of $K^{\beta\gamma}$ and $K^{\beta\alpha}$ are opposite and the values of $K^{\beta\gamma}$ are greater than $K^{\beta\alpha}$, which shows that the migration direction of the interface γ/β and β/α is opposite, and the migration distance of the interface γ/β is greater than the interface β/α . This is in agreement with the reported experimental results [5, 6, 11]. According to Eq.8, the parabolic coefficient of β phase K is controlled by D^β , $K^{\beta\gamma}$ and $K^{\beta\alpha}$. Furthermore, the values of $K^{\beta\gamma}$ and $K^{\beta\alpha}$ are controlled by the difference of interfacial equilibrium concentration $C^{\alpha\beta} - C^{\beta\alpha}$, $C^{\beta\alpha} - C^{\alpha\beta}$, $C^{\beta\gamma} - C^{\beta\alpha}$, $C^{\beta\gamma} - C^{\beta\alpha}$, $C^{\gamma\beta} - C^{\beta\gamma}$, $C^{\gamma\beta} - C^{\beta\gamma}$ and the ratios of inter-diffusion coefficient D^β/D^α , D^β/D^γ from Eq.6 and Eq.7. Since the equilibrium concentration of α , β and γ phases is almost constant in the temperature range of 793-848K, the influence of the interfacial equilibrium concentration difference on the values of $K^{\beta\gamma}$ and $K^{\beta\alpha}$ can be ignored. However, although the values D^β/D^α and D^β/D^γ vary significantly, most of the values of $(K^{\beta\gamma} - K^{\beta\alpha})^2$ are approximately constant to be $1.1-1.2 \times 10^{-2}$ as D^β is much greater than D^α and D^γ , which shows that the value of the effective diffusion coefficient D^α has small direct influence on the growth of TiAl_3 . In general, the growth of TiAl_3 is largely dominated by the effective inter-diffusion coefficient of D^β . As seen from Table 1, D^β is controlled by the grain size and shape, the annealing temperature, and the activation energy of volume and grain boundary diffusion, and is regulated by different processes and chemical composition [8, 9, 19]. This is the reason why the growth rate constant varies widely in the reported data.

Process parameter	$D^\beta(\text{m}^2/\text{s})$	$D^\alpha(\text{m}^2/\text{s})$	$D^\gamma(\text{m}^2/\text{s})$	D^β/D^α	D^β/D^γ	$K^{\beta\gamma}$	$K^{\beta\alpha}$	$(K^{\beta\gamma} - K^{\beta\alpha})^2$	$K(\text{m}^2/\text{s})$
793K, $Q_{\beta\text{gb}}/Q_{\beta\text{v}} = 0.5$ $d_\alpha = 7\mu\text{m}$, $d_\beta = 3\mu\text{m}$, $d_\gamma = \infty$	3.53×10^{-15}	4.85×10^{-20}	8.37×10^{-19}	7.28×10^4	4.22×10^3	-7.61×10^{-2}	2.98×10^{-2}	1.12×10^{-2}	1.58×10^{-16}
823K, $Q_{\beta\text{gb}}/Q_{\beta\text{v}} = 0.5$ $d_\alpha = 7\mu\text{m}$, $d_\beta = 3\mu\text{m}$, $d_\gamma = \infty$	5.65×10^{-15}	1.48×10^{-19}	3.52×10^{-18}	3.81×10^4	1.61×10^3	-7.61×10^{-2}	3.00×10^{-2}	1.13×10^{-2}	2.54×10^{-16}
848K, $Q_{\beta\text{gb}}/Q_{\beta\text{v}} = 0.5$ $d_\alpha = 7\mu\text{m}$, $d_\beta = 3\mu\text{m}$, $d_\gamma = \infty$	8.19×10^{-15}	3.55×10^{-19}	1.08×10^{-17}	2.31×10^4	7.59×10^2	-7.61×10^{-2}	3.02×10^{-2}	1.13×10^{-2}	3.70×10^{-16}
848K, $Q_{\beta\text{gb}}/Q_{\beta\text{v}} = 0.4$ $d_\alpha = 7\mu\text{m}$, $d_\beta = 3\mu\text{m}$, $d_\gamma = \infty$	8.25×10^{-14}	3.55×10^{-19}	1.08×10^{-17}	2.33×10^5	7.65×10^3	-7.61×10^{-2}	3.02×10^{-2}	1.13×10^{-2}	3.70×10^{-15}
848K, $Q_{\beta\text{gb}}/Q_{\beta\text{v}} = 0.6$ $d_\alpha = 7\mu\text{m}$, $d_\beta = 3\mu\text{m}$, $d_\gamma = \infty$	1.11×10^{-15}	3.55×10^{-19}	1.08×10^{-17}	3.14×10^3	1.03×10^2	-8.12×10^{-2}	2.91×10^{-2}	1.22×10^{-2}	5.40×10^{-17}
848K, $Q_{\beta\text{gb}}/Q_{\beta\text{v}} = 0.5$ $d_\alpha = 7\mu\text{m}$, $d_\beta = 0.2\mu\text{m}$, $d_\gamma = \infty$	1.18×10^{-13}	3.55×10^{-19}	1.08×10^{-17}	3.32×10^5	1.09×10^4	-7.61×10^{-2}	3.02×10^{-2}	1.13×10^{-2}	5.33×10^{-15}
848K, $Q_{\beta\text{gb}}/Q_{\beta\text{v}} = 0.5$ $d_\alpha = 7\mu\text{m}$, $d_\beta = 1\mu\text{m}$, $d_\gamma = \infty$	2.38×10^{-14}	3.55×10^{-19}	1.08×10^{-17}	6.73×10^4	2.21×10^3	-7.61×10^{-2}	3.02×10^{-2}	1.13×10^{-2}	1.08×10^{-15}
848K, $Q_{\beta\text{gb}}/Q_{\beta\text{v}} = 0.5$ $d_\alpha = 7\mu\text{m}$, $d_\beta = 7\mu\text{m}$, $d_\gamma = \infty$	3.72×10^{-15}	3.55×10^{-19}	1.08×10^{-17}	1.05×10^4	3.45×10^2	-7.67×10^{-2}	3.00×10^{-2}	1.14×10^{-2}	1.70×10^{-16}
848K, $Q_{\beta\text{gb}}/Q_{\beta\text{v}} = 0.5$ $d_\alpha = 1\mu\text{m}$, $d_\beta = 3\mu\text{m}$, $d_\gamma = \infty$	8.19×10^{-15}	2.45×10^{-18}	1.08×10^{-17}	3.30×10^3	7.59×10^2	-7.61×10^{-2}	3.02×10^{-2}	1.13×10^{-2}	3.70×10^{-16}
848K, $Q_{\beta\text{gb}}/Q_{\beta\text{v}} = 0.5$ $d_\alpha = 3\mu\text{m}$, $d_\beta = 3\mu\text{m}$, $d_\gamma = \infty$	8.19×10^{-15}	8.27×10^{-19}	1.08×10^{-17}	9.91×10^3	7.59×10^2	-7.61×10^{-2}	3.02×10^{-2}	1.13×10^{-2}	3.70×10^{-16}
848K, $Q_{\beta\text{gb}}/Q_{\beta\text{v}} = 0.5$ $d_\alpha = 14\mu\text{m}$, $d_\beta = 3\mu\text{m}$, $d_\gamma = \infty$	8.19×10^{-15}	1.77×10^{-19}	1.08×10^{-17}	4.62×10^4	7.59×10^2	-7.61×10^{-2}	3.02×10^{-2}	1.13×10^{-2}	3.70×10^{-16}
848K, $Q_{\beta\text{gb}}/Q_{\beta\text{v}} = 0.5$ $d_\alpha = 28\mu\text{m}$, $d_\beta = 3\mu\text{m}$, $d_\gamma = \infty$	8.19×10^{-15}	8.87×10^{-20}	1.08×10^{-17}	9.23×10^4	7.59×10^2	-7.61×10^{-2}	3.02×10^{-2}	1.13×10^{-2}	3.70×10^{-16}
848K, $Q_{\beta\text{gb}}/Q_{\beta\text{v}} = 0.5$ $d_\alpha = 56\mu\text{m}$, $d_\beta = 3\mu\text{m}$, $d_\gamma = \infty$	8.19×10^{-15}	4.44×10^{-20}	1.08×10^{-17}	1.84×10^5	7.59×10^2	-7.61×10^{-2}	3.02×10^{-2}	1.13×10^{-2}	3.70×10^{-16}

Table 1: The calculated values of kinetics parameter of Ti/Al diffusion bonding.

Under the conditions of $d_\beta = 3\mu\text{m}$, $d_\alpha = 7\mu\text{m}$, $Q_{\beta\text{gb}}/Q_{\beta\text{v}} = 0.5$, the growth rate constant of β phase is 1.58×10^{-16} , 2.54×10^{-16} , $3.70 \times 10^{-16} \text{m}^2/\text{s}$ at 793, 823, 848K, respectively, which are close to the experimental results by LIU et al[11] and XU et al[6] at the same conditions. Furthermore, the

concentration profiles of Al in all of phases for 6h annealing time are plotted with solid lines in Fig. 3, which are also similar to the experimental results by LIU et al under the same conditions (Fig. 3d) [11]. Several characteristics can be seen from Fig. 3. 1) Ti atoms are almost absent in γ phase, which is due to the facts that the solubility of Ti in γ phase is very low, and the inter-diffusion coefficient of Ti in γ phase is very small; 2) the concentration profiles of Al in β phase are nearly linear (Fig. 3b), which is because the inter-diffusion coefficient of β phase is high and the concentration range of β phase is very narrow; 3) a small count of Al atoms is present in α phase since the solid solubility of Al in α phase is relatively large. However, because the inter-diffusion coefficient of Al in α phase is low, the diffusion depths are very short, which show that Ti and Al atoms rarely appear in the opposite side of the solid solution and are almost used to form the TiAl_3 phase.

Figure 3: The concentration profiles of Al in all the phases of Ti/Al diffusion couple for different time at 848K for 6h, (a) γ phase, (b) β phase, (c) α phase and (d) the experimental data by LIU at the same conditions (the initial thickness of TiAl_3 is $0.5\mu\text{m}$ before the diffusion couple is annealed) [11].

5 CONCLUSIONS

(1) A theoretical model has been developed for studying the isothermal reaction diffusion below the melting temperature of aluminium based on the Ti/Al solid phase reactive diffusion mechanism.

(2) The growth kinetics of TiAl_3 is mainly controlled by the inter-diffusion coefficient of TiAl_3 , and the diffusion coefficient of TiAl_3 is mainly dominated by the grain boundary diffusion, which is decided by the size and shape of TiAl_3 phase, the temperature and active energy of diffusion.

(3) The diffusion coefficients of Al element in α phase and Ti element in γ phase are very small and the solubility of Ti element in γ phase is low, therefore, Ti and Al atoms rarely appear in the opposite side of the solid solution and are almost used to form the TiAl_3 phase.

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